

The Economic Base of Tikrit City

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Received: 7 July 2020, Revised: 26 July 2020, Accepted: 5 August 2020, Online: 10 August 2020

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the economic structure of Tikrit City, using one of the important tools of the economic base theory, to determine the structure and composition of the local economy. This research shows which sector “drive” the local economy by generating outside income for the community. This paper studies the application of the location quotient technique, its theoretical framework, and its application as a regional economic technique, and its affection on the regional and local economy. Findings of this study indicate that the Service sector is becoming the leading sector in Tikrit city represent with education and health sector. The study suggests a group of proposals that could help to use the regional economic technique including: it is necessary to issue annual statistics and make them available to researcher. Give more attention to data of the labor force, its movement within the country and its regions and documented it to facilitate the task of researchers.

Keywords: Salah al-Din Governorate, Economic Base, Tikrit City, Local Economy, Location quotient, Iraq.

1. Introduction

The ultimate goal of local and regional policy makers is to improve the well being of local population and promote opportunity and equity for them, which is possible only by increasing the competitive edge of their respective regions. To do so policy makers requires sound policies of local and regional development , based on the analysis of economic and social infrastructure , political , and this requires a number of tools of economic analysis , which is among the decision-making tools most reliable policy-makers , regional and local to prioritize support spectral and spatially .

In the age of globalization, the role of countries is almost replaced by cities. To improve urban competitiveness is the mandate of government

efforts, the future shape of the city is not fixed and that is the key point of city competitiveness, particularly when cities are dormant and include a static population and a static movement etc. The future city will be the triangular framework of pull, push and weight. Push of future includes globalization, urbanization, population structure, localization, environmental movement, cultural creativity and innovative technology. Pull of future includes post-modern industrial city, the global science and technology city, world city and multi-cultural cities, and weight includes improved infrastructure, sustainable resources, urban landscape, etc.(Wen- Fong Huang, 2010).

It is important for national authorities to help and encourage cities and smaller towns to strengthen their attractiveness by upgrading the quality of the

environment and by providing for the better utilization of the potential of local cultural and natural resources and identity. Urban areas of different sizes play important and different roles in regional development (Nordic and Regions, 2006).

Cities are a major form of the material, social and symbolic organization of societies. They are persistent and adaptive structures which fulfill a variety of social functionalities: habitat, production, services, political control over people and territories, as well as technical and symbolic mediation between nature and culture, groups and individuals. For a long time, and especially since the first industrial revolution, they have been both the spaces where most innovations occur and spaces for which most innovations are designed (Bretagnolle A., 2009).

There are a lot of tools that help to describe and document and analyze changes in the local economy, including help and can make sound decisions and informed, and use these models on a large scale, because of its simplicity and ease of use, in order to develop local or national economy after knowing the reality of the situation and study it carefully to see strengths and weaknesses and then comes the next step to address the weaknesses and strengths. The fundamental problem is how to identify and measure the economic base of an area. Several methods have been used to define what constitutes the economic base; here we discuss and apply the Economic Base Theory which provides an overall framework to understand and specific tools to analyze the local economy of Tikrit city.

2. Problem Statement

The local economy is strongest when it develops those economic sectors that are not closely tied to the local economy. By developing businesses and industries that rely primarily on external markets, these external markets will remain strong even if the local economy experiences problems. In contrast local economy wholly dependent upon local factors will have great trouble responding to economic slumps.

In other word, the decision maker requires to know the economic reality, specialization, diversity, consumer industries, and production industries, for domestic consumption or for export..... Etc. Identify the economic base of cities whether it is an agricultural or industrial or tourist in order to develop these sectors, this prompted the researcher to choose this topic to address one of the important tools which analyze the economic structure of local and regional issues.

2.1 The Study Purpose

Cities are the engines of national economic prosperity. The purpose of the study is identifying the structure of the local economy and future opportunities and constraints for Tikrit city depending upon location quotient technique which represent the most important tool of the economic base theory tools.

2.2 The Importance and Objectives of Research

The importance of study is to show the techniques that can contribute significantly to analysis the local economic structure in an easy and simple manner. The research aims to:

1. Identifying some techniques that can help us in the analysis process.
2. Clarify the mechanism of use these methods in the analysis of the local economy.
3. Identify the economic base of Tikrit city by using location quotient tool.
4. Give some recommendations that can help to use this method.

3. Background Theory of the Study

3.1 The Beginning of Economic Base Analysis

Economic base analysis was developed by Robert Murray Haig in his work on the Regional Plan of New York in 1928. Briefly, activities in an area divide into two categories – basic and non-basic. Basic industries are those exporting from the region and bringing wealth from outside; non-basic (or service) industries support basic industries. (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Economic_base_analysis)

3.2 Economic-base Concepts

An “Economic Base Analysis” is an analytical tool used to profile a local economy and compare it to a reference area. The economic base of an area consists of those activities that provide the core employment and income on which the rest of the local economy depends. Concerns about what constitutes the economic base and its size are part of trying to understand how various activities might affect opportunities for the people living in the area and those whose well-being depends on the level of economic activity in the area (Lisa K. Crone, April 1999).

According to Klosterman (1990), "The economic base technique is based on a simple causal model that assumes that the basic sector is the prime cause of local economic growth, that it is the economic base of the local economy" (Klosterman, 1990).

Economic-base concepts originated with the need to predict the effects of new economic activity on cities and regions. Say a new plant is located in our city. It directly employs a certain number of people. In a market economy these employees depend on others to provide food, housing, clothing, education, protection and other requirements of the good life. The question which city planners and economists need to answer, then, is "what are the indirect effects of this new activity on employment and income in the community?" With these estimates in hand, we can work toward planning the social infrastructure needed to support all of these people (WASchaffer, 2010)..

3.3 The Importance of the Economic Base

One of the most commonly used models to describe the functioning of local economies is Economic Base Theory. Why is the basic/non-basic distinction important? Economic Base Theory asserts that the means of strengthening and growing the local economy is to develop and enhance the basic sector. The basic sector is therefore identified as the "engine" of the local economy. Economic Base Theory also posits that the local economy is strongest when it develops those economic sectors that are not closely tied to the local economy. By developing firms that rely primarily on external markets (Solution, 2005).

3.4 Economic Base Assumptions

As H. Craig Davis explain that the model have several fundamental assumptions, the most obvious five are:

1. The first is that exports are the sole source of regional economic growth (investment, government spending, and household consumption are ignored).
2. The second assumption that the export industry is homogeneous (i.e., that an increase or decrease of one export does not affect another).
3. The third assumption is the constancy of the export/service ratio over the period.
4. The fourth assumption is the absence of interregional feedback or there is no inter-regional feedback.
5. The fifth assumption is a pool of underutilized resources (Davis, 2001).

3.5 Economic Base Technique

The economic base technique is grounded in the assumption that the local economy can be divided into two very general sectors:

1. **Basic Sector:** This sector is made up of local businesses (firms) that are entirely dependent upon external factors. For example, Boeing builds and sells large airplanes to companies and countries located throughout the world. Their business is dependent almost entirely upon non-local firms. Boeing does not sell planes to families or households locally, so their business is very much dependent upon exporting their goods. Manufacturing and local resource-oriented firms (like logging or mining) are usually considered to be basic sector firms because their fortunes depend largely upon non-local factors, they usually export their goods.

2. **Non-basic Sector:** The non-basic sector, in contrast, is composed of those firms that depend largely upon local business conditions. For example, a local grocery store sells its goods to local households, businesses, and individuals. Its clientele is locally based and, therefore, its products are consumed locally. Almost all local services (like drycleaners, restaurants, and drug stores) are identified as non-basic because they depend almost entirely on local factors.

3.6 The Component of the Basic Sector

The basic sector consists of the following activities (Lopes, 2000-2005) :

- A. Activities that bring money into the local economy
- B. Activities that meet external demand (external demand)
- C. Activities that depend on factors outside the domestic economy

Typical activities of the basic sector:

1. Agriculture
2. Mining
3. Manufacturing
4. Forestry
5. local government services state and local government
6. Tourist activities

The non basic sector consists of: Activities that use money in the local economy , Activities that meet

local demand , Patterns of non-basic sector activities:

1. The activities of the local government
2. Local retailing
3. Local school district
4. Building construction
5. The local utilities or services Local utilities

3.7 Economic Base process Requirement

Klosterman identifies two key decisions that need to be made at the beginning of this analytical process:

1. Identify your study area: It is important to note that the "local economy" means different things to different people. As a planner for the city the local economy may mean identify the boundaries of the local economy versus the external world. It is also important to note that this will have a significant impact upon your results as the economic base model is grounded upon the distinction between the local and the external economies.

2. Select Your Measurement Units: Economic base analysis usually is undertaken using Employment data. This unit of analysis, the number of jobs, is most common because employment data is available from the Census Bureau. However, these same techniques can be used on other economic units like Payroll and Sales and Value Added (Klosterman, 1990).

3.8 Economic Base Analysis methods

There are number of ways to analyze the strengths/weaknesses, specializations, and overall diversity of the local economy. The three techniques below offer planners a set of simple, but popular tools to perform such analyses. These techniques also illustrate core principles underlying the quantitative analysis of data by the planning profession.

I. Assumption Technique: It is by far the simplest economic analysis tool available to planners. This method estimates local Basic sector employment by using a fundamental set of assumptions about the local economy.

II. Location Quotient Technique: The Location Quotient Technique determines the level of Basic sector employment by comparing the local economy to the economy of a larger geographic unit like the governorate or the entire country. The location quotient is often employed to quantify industrial concentration in regions. Moreover, the location quotient has long been applied to estimate

the strength of regional economic impacts and export (economic-base) activities, Researchers usually assume that if the calculated location quotient is above one, then the industry is concentrated in that particular region (Guimarães et al., 2009) .The formula for computing location quotients can be written as:

$$LQ = \frac{e_i/e}{E_i/E}$$

Where:

- e_i = Local employment in industry i
- e = Total local employment
- E_i = Reference area employment in industry i
- E = Total reference area employment

It is assumed that the base year is identical in all of the above variables.

The location quotient is a useful tool for comparing area characteristics. It has applications in areas such as health care and economics (Moineddin et al., 2003).The location quotient (LQ) ratio, a measure designed to quantify and benchmark the degree of relative concentration of an activity in the analysis of area localization, has received considerable attention in the geographic and economics literature (Beyene and Moineddin, 2005).

III. Minimum Requirements Technique: The Minimum Requirements Technique is the most complex economic base analysis method. This method compares the local economy with the economies of a sample of similarly sized regions.

4. The Economic Base of Tikrit City

4.1 Salah al-Din Governorate, Location, and population

Salah al-Din governorate, located in the north of the capital Baghdad and away from Up to 165 km and is bordered by the provinces of Nineveh and Erbil from North Sulaimaniya, Kirkuk and Diyala and from the east and south of Baghdad and Anbar From the West. Enjoy Salah al-Din province, an important geographical location being Node transportation between northern and southern provinces (Iraq, 2012).

The Population of Salah al-Din governorate: 1.259 Million, Labor Force: 618,000, Area : 24,363 sq. km., Capital: Tikrit , One of the main roads leading north from Baghdad heads to Samarra and Tikrit,

also passing Bayji on its way to Mosul. From Tikrit, a primary road heads northeast to Kirkuk. A main road also crosses the province at Bayji, running northeast to Kirkuk and southwest to Haditha in Al Anbar province and on the Al-Qaim border crossing with Syria. Iraq's major north-south rail line passes through Salah al-Din, with service from Baghdad to Mosul via Tikrit(Iraq, 2012).55% of the governorate's workforce is employed in the agricultural sector, the highest percentage among all 18 governorates. The governorate has a huge number of grape vines, apple trees and citrus trees under cultivation.

4.2 The location of Tikrit City

Tikrit city is the capital of Salah Al-Din governorate. It lies on the west bank of the Tigris, about 100 miles (160 km) northwest of Baghdad. In

the 10th century Tikrit had a fortress and was home to a large Christian monastery. Its wealth at that time derived from its production of woollen fabrics. Salah al-Din, the Muslim founder of the Ayobeyeen dynasty, was born at Tikrit about 1137, the modern province of which Tikrit is the capital is named after him, (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tikrit). Tikrit remains one of the important centers of Christianity until the year 1164, after this date the seat of a chair of Maphryono Yacoubi had transferred to the city of Mosul. Now, Tikrit is a modern city with population of (190, 220) , (1011184) urban , represent 17% of the urban population ,and (88979) rural , represent 12% of rural population in Salah al-Din governorate (Planning, 1992).

Map 1: Map of land use in Tikrit city

Source: [www. Maps of cities in Iraq](http://www.Maps of cities in Iraq)

4.3 The Economic Base of Tikrit City

The location quotient is a useful tool for comparing area characteristics. It has applications in areas such as health care and economics. Location quotient play an important role in comparing; area characteristics. In order to indicate the economic base of Tikrit city , we will review the location quotient of some activities in salah al-Din governorate to see which activities are concentrated in Tikrit city, as follows:

4.4 Economic Activities

Industry and Agriculture are the most important economic activities in cities or regions in general, which can enhance the economic potential through

the provision of money depending on exports to other cities and regions, as well as coverage of local needs. The importance of these activities could be illustrated through the use of the location quotient of Industrial and agricultural labor force to know the strength or weakness of each activity in any city of salah al-Din governorate.

4.5 Industrial Labor Force

Baiji city occupies the first rank in the relative importance of the industrial labor force with location quotient (2.17) , followed by the city of Samarra which got (1.94), while Tikrit city occupies the sixth rank and does not have any importance in the field of industry, as shown in table 1.

Table 1: The location quotient of Industrial labor force for salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Total labor force	Industrial labor force	location quotient	Rank
Tikrit	33227	1716	0.43	6
Dujail	11292	533	0.40	7
Balad	26138	1721	0.56	5
Samarra	23857	5455	1.94	2
Aldour	6814	229	0.28	8
Tuze	19250	2163	0.95	3
Baiji	21503	5484	2.17	1
Shurqat	16179	1282	0.67	4
Sum	158260	18583		

Source: (Ministry of Planning, 2012)

4.6 Agriculture Labor Force

The first rank of location quotient of agricultural labor force was for Dujail city which got **(2.98)** , followed by the city of Balad that occupied the

second rank with location quotient **(2.34)** , while the city of Tikrit occupies the sixth rank and does not have any importance in the field of agricultural labor force, as shown in table 2.

Table 2: The location quotient of agricultural labor force for salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Total labor force	Agriculture labor force	location quotient	Rank
Tikrit	33227	1614	0.41	6
Dujail	11292	3953	2.98	1
Balad	26138	7203	2.34	2
Samarra	23857	1397	0.49	4
Aldour	6814	38	0.04	8
Tuze	19250	1076	0.47	5
Baiji	21503	559	0.22	7
Shurqat	16179	2993	1.57	3
Sum	158260	18833		

Source: (Ministry of Planning, 2012)

4.7 Socio-Economic Activities

The education and health service activities considered as an important socio-economic activities , and these activities could be the economic base for many cities .to explain the importance of these activities in Salah al-Din governorate cities we will use the location quotient of educational and health labor force in these cities .

4.8 Educational Labor Force

The city of Tikrit considered as a center of educational services in salah al-Din governorate. It has a large number of schools as well as the presence of Tikrit University in it , which includes more than 16 college, and this enhanced it to get the first rank in the Educational labor force with location quotient (**1.40**), this mean that the economic base of Tikrit city is the educational service, as shown in table 3.

Table 3: The location quotient of Educational labor force for salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Total labor force	education labor force	location quotient	Rank
Tikrit	33227	7080	1.40	1
Dujail	11292	1746	1.02	4
Balad	26138	3293	0.83	5
Samarra	23857	2806	0.77	7
Aldour	6814	1171	1.13	3
Tuze	19250	3749	1.28	2
Baiji	21503	2144	0.65	8
Shurqat	16179	1959	0.80	6
Sum	158260	23948		

Source: (Ministry of Planning, 2012)

4.9 Health Labor Force

Tikrit city is the main center of health services in salah al-Din governorate because it has many healt centers which serve the governorate as a whole , this mean it has the largest number of health labor force ,represent with the location quotient of health

labor force (**2.18**) , and this enhanced it to obtain the first rank in the governorate , this activity considered as basic activity in Tikrit city. The local economy was specialized in health and educational services confirmed by looking at these sectors concentrations, as shown in table 4.

Table 4: The location quotient of Health labor force for Salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Total labor force	health labor force	location quotient	Rank
Tikrit	33227	3414	2.18	1
Dujail	11292	211	0.39	8
Balad	26138	670	0.54	6
Samarra	23857	627	0.55	5
Aldour	6814	142	0.44	7
Tuze	19250	1263	1.39	2
Baiji	21503	655	0.64	3
Shurqat	16179	454	0.59	4
Sum	158260	7436		

Source: (Ministry of Planning, 2012)

4.10 Health Organizations

Tikrit city has (275) health organizations from (931) health organizations in the governorate as a whole, represent about 30%. The presence of these organizations help Tikrit city to get the first rank in

Salah al-Din governorate with location quotient of health organizations (2.01). This result enhances the foregoing that we talked about, and reinforces the previous result of the fact that the economic base of Tikrit city is the health in addition to education services.

Table 5: The location quotient of Health Organizations for salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Total organizations	Health organizations	location quotient	Rank
Tikrit	9350	275	2.01	1
Dujail	4101	50	0.83	5
Balad	14479	121	0.57	8
Samarra	10488	113	0.73	7
Aldour	2410	39	1.10	3
Tuze	7187	127	1.21	2
Baiji	6724	104	1.05	4
Shurqat	9024	102	0.77	6
Sum	63763	931		

Source: (Ministry of Planning, 2012)

4.11 Educational institutions

The educational institutions represent the important requirements of the infrastructure of any city, to cover the needs of the city and provide additional seats to the people from outside the city. It contributes to creating a safe learning environment, and then provides enough money for the city. There

are (242) educational institution in the city of Tikrit, constitute (24%) of the educational institutions in the province as a whole. The presence of these Educational institutions help Tikrit city to get the first rank in salah al-Din governorate with location quotient (1.51) as shown in table 6, this result demonstrates the administrative and service function of the city of Tikrit.

Table 6: The location quotient of Educational institutions for salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Total organizations	educational organizations	location quotient	Rank
Tikrit	7521	242	1.51	1
Dujail	4101	121	1.39	3
Balad	4104	57	0.65	8
Samarra	8989	139	0.72	7
Aldour	2410	82	1.60	2
Tuze	5117	87	0.80	6
Baiji	5894	102	0.81	5
Shurqat	9024	169	0.88	4
Sum	47160	999		

Source: (Ministry of Planning, 2012)

The calculated location quotient for the main activities in salah al-Din governorate cities could be summarized as shown in table 7, which clarified the economic base of the city of Tikrit, through its index, when it is above one, then the activity is

concentrated in Tikrit city , otherwise it has not any importance. So the main activities that concentrated in tikrit city are education and health services.

Table 7: summary of the calculated location quotient for salah al-Din governorate cities for the year 2011

City	Industrial labor force L.Q	Agriculture labor force L.Q	Health labor force L.Q	Health Organizations L.Q	Education institutions L.Q	Education labor force L.Q
Tikrit	0.43	0.41	2.18	2.01	1.51	1.40
Dujail	0.40	2.98	0.39	0.83	1.39	1.02
Balad	0.56	2.34	0.54	0.57	0.65	0.83
Samarra	1.94	0.49	0.55	0.73	0.72	0.77
Aldour	0.28	0.04	0.44	1.10	1.60	1.13
Tuze	0.95	0.47	1.39	1.21	0.80	1.28
Baiji	2.17	0.22	0.64	1.05	0.81	0.65
Shurqat	0.67	1.57	0.59	0.77	0.88	0.80
Sum						

5. Conclusions

Some conclusions appear reasonable, based on this analysis:

1. It is important to note that the Service sector is becoming the leading employment sector in tikrit city represent with education and health sector.
2. The use of quantitative methods gives much clearer and more confident of results to the decision maker.
3. These tools describes specialty of areas, and the pattern of a particular economic regions, that would facilitate promotion of this pattern if there is a tendency for it, and through these studies can be found on the map of national and regional economic specialization in the country.
4. The economic base illustrates the leading export sectors in the regions and this makes the decision maker easy to achieve diversity, specialization and the development of these sectors in the cities.

5. The location quotient shows the concentration of the economic or social activities through the labor force concentration of a particular activity in a particular region or area. As well as determined the basic and non-basic labors force.
6. By using these methods we can identify strengths and weaknesses in the local economy compared with similar economies in the regions

6. Recommendations

1. More attention must be given to the main and basic activities (health and education) in the city of Tikrit as they represent the economic base of this city. They are the economic artery that provides income from abroad.
2. Due to the importance of statistics, it is necessary to issue annual statistics and put them available to researchers.
3. There is great need to establish a special classification for industries in developing countries similar to that found in developed

countries, "Standard Industrial Classification or standard" Standard Industrial Classification.

4. More Attention must be given to data of the labor force and its movement within the country and documented them to facilitate the task of researchers and users of analysis methods in the process of economic analysis of the regional structure.
5. It is necessary to provide special data related to the size of the population and the labor force in the regions studied, the rates of population growth, as well as per capita income and the level of unemployment compared to the national level and other regions.

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